

Bhimthadi Horse: Pages of Glory Lost in the Books of History

(Eighth registered horse breed of India)

Sharat Chandra Mehta, Ranjeet D Pawar, Ratna Prabha*, Sachin D Sorate, Suhaib Qureshi,

T.K. Bhattacharya

ICAR-National Research Centre on Equines, Regional Station,

Equine Production Campus, Bikaner-334001, India

Abstract

Bhimthadi (Deccani) horses, once an integral part of the cavalry of the Maratha army, were almost lost to history and were considered to be on the verge of extinction, along with the Chumarti and Sikang breeds. The Centre took the initiative and conducted an extensive survey, which led to the identification of purebred animals in the districts of Pune, Ahmednagar, Satara, Sangli, Solapur, and Kolhapur in Maharashtra. The population of the breed was estimated to be 5134 in the year 2023, with very few quality stallions and mares remaining in the breeding tract. The predominant coat colour of the Bhimthadi horse is chestnut. The forehead is generally flat, and the ears are relatively large; their tips do not meet or overlap when rotated. The hooves are nearly round in shape, with strong soles and walls. The back is moderate and slightly arched. The average height at withers, body length, heart girth, and body weight were recorded as 130.3 ± 0.20 cm, 132.5 ± 0.25 cm, 142.0 ± 0.56 cm, and 266.77 ± 2.22 kg for stallions, and 129.7 ± 0.37 cm, 131.7 ± 0.42 cm, 139.7 ± 0.98 cm, and 252.18 ± 3.76 kg for mares. The breed is now Gazette Notified as the eighth indigenous horse breed of India, with Accession No. INDIA_HORSE_1100_BHIMTHADI_07008. Conservation and propagation efforts are currently underway through the formation of the *All India Bhimthadi Horse Association* and the organization of regular shows and events.

Keywords: Bhimathdi, horses, equine conservation, breed recognition

Introduction

Described as “one of the best breeds in India” by the colonial-era botanist Sir George Watt, the Bhimthadi horse derives its name from the Bhima River valley in the Pune district of Maharashtra, where it originated. The term "*thadi*" means riverbank in the local language. It is also known as *Nirathadi*, as the breed is found along the banks of the Nira River, a major tributary of the Bhima River. Additionally, it is referred to as Deccani due to its distribution across the Deccan Plateau in India. The Bhimthadi breed was developed in Pune district in 17th and 18th centuries during the Maratha rule. These horses proved excellent for Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj's forces in fighting the Mughal army in the hilly terrains of Western Maharashtra. It is also mentioned that Sardar Yashwantrao Holkar Maharaj used to ride on the Bhimthadi mare named “*Mahua*” in the battle fields. Bhimthadi horse gets mention in different historical documents.

During early 19th century (Philloptt, 1911), Rangin, a poet and author of Persian-language wrote: “*Were you to ask me where the best horses are found, I would say first of all in Bhimrathal (Bhima Terai is the valley of the Bhima River, famed for its breed of hardy ponies and horses. The breed is known in Northern India as the Bhimrathali.); its horses are hardy and capable of travelling long stages on meagre food. Next to these are the horses of Kathiyawar. Nearly, but not quite, equal to them are the horses of Narjangel. Compared to these three breeds all others are asses*”. In 1832, Lt. Col. James Tod, in his pioneer work on history and geography of India (Tod, 1832), mentioned: “*The bard then describes the steeds of the Rajput chivalry, in which the Bhimthadi (or Bhivarthadi were highly esteemed by Marathas) of the Deccan takes precedence; he is followed by the horses of Dhat and Rardara in Marwar, and the Kathiawar of Saurashtra*”. Lt. Col. Tod's work was also cited by Abhimanyu Singh Arha (2016) in *Hoofprint of Empire: An Environmental History of Fodder in Mughal India (1650–1850)* (Arsh, 2016), where he reiterated the reputation of the Maratha Bhimthadi breed

as the finest among all in India. In the Gazetteer of Bombay Presidency: Ahmadnagar (1884) by James M. Campbell (1884), it is noted: "*Of Horses, Mares, and Foals, the 1882-83 returns showed a total of 18,978. Ahmadnagar, especially the Bhima valley, was once famous for its horses. Now horses are few and poor. After 1803, when the English became responsible for the peace of the Deccan the Nagar breed of horses seems to have been allowed to decline. In 1877, 359 mares served. Almost all well - to - do Kunbis have a mare or two, the Bhimthadi mares being worth £ 20 to £ 40 (Rs. 200-400)*". These were among the best warrior horses, and were also widely used by the local people for travelling from one place to another.

The literature suggests that after the early 19th century, the Bhimthadi breed deteriorated significantly. Until recently, the population of the Bhimthadi horse was listed as only 100 by the Domestic Animal Diversity Information System (DAD-IS) of the FAO and categorized as critically endangered. A study conducted by Khadka (2010), also classified the breed under the same category.

Traditional animal fairs for the breed are still held, and a considerable number of Bhimthadi horses are sold and purchased at the *Yeola* Horse Fair in Ahmednagar district, Maharashtra. This fair is popularly known as "*Yeola ka Dasher Ghoda Mela*." Another fair dedicated to the breed is organized on *Kojagiri Purnima* at Salpe village in Phaltan taluka of Satara district, Maharashtra. These horses continue to serve the nomadic communities for transportation. A significant number of male animals are also utilized by various companies for the production of anti-sera against specific pathogens or etiological agents. Additionally, Bhimthadi horses are still used in traditional sports such as bullock racing and Tonga races in different parts of Maharashtra, India.

In spite of this glorious history, the country had seven registered breeds of indigenous horses viz. Marwari, Kathiawari, K-Sindhi, Manipuri, Zanskari, Spiti and Bhutia. The Bhimthadi (Deccani) horses were referred as at the verge of extinction along with the Chumarti

and Sikang breeds (Breed-wise Report of Livestock and Poultry, 2022; Gupta et al., 2012 and 2014). In order to bring back the glory to this historic breed, this study was planned for the characterisation and recognition of Bhimthadi horses in India.

Materials and Methods

Attempts have been made to recognize the Bhimthadi as an independent breed (Mehta et al., 2024), which is a primary requirement for its conservation and propagation. An extensive survey covering approximately 74,329 km² was conducted across the major distribution areas of this horse, including the districts of Pune, Ahmednagar (Ahilyanagar), Satara, Solapur, Sangli, and Kolhapur in Maharashtra, India. The breeding tract of the Bhimthadi horse extends from 15.7469°N to 19.9897°N latitude and from 73.3249°E to 76.414°E longitude.

Fig. 1: Breeding tract of Bhimthadi breed of horse encompassing Pune, Ahmednagar (Ahilyanagar), Sangli, Satara, Kolhapur and Solapur districts in Maharashtra state of India.

The population of horses in the above districts (Livestock Census, 2019) and the availability of Bhimthadi horses were considered for planning the study. The identification of pure Bhimthadi animals was ascertained by going through the literature and holding of workshop with the well-known horse breeders of Pune, Ahmednagar, Sangli, Satara, Solapur

and Kolhapur at the Agriculture Development Trust, Baramati in Pune district of Maharashtra. This workshop was followed by visit to the breeding tract where the animals were examined and the criteria were fixed. In order to overcome the biasness in measurement by different enumerators, two theoretical presentations followed by field visit for hands-on training were organised by the senior author himself. The statistical analysis of the data, for calculation of mean, standard error, range and effect of sex; was carried out using IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 26) software. The body weights were taken with a tape (heart girth correlated with body weight) and verified for Bhimthadi horse by actually weighting the horses on a weight bridge. The highest horse population was recorded in Pune (2,934 heads), followed by Ahmednagar (2,412), Kolhapur (920), Satara (751), Solapur (640), and Sangli (466). Although Ahmednagar district had the second-highest horse population, the number of pure Bhimthadi horses was relatively low. Accordingly, a total of 379 adult animals belonging to 112 households from Pune (58), Ahmednagar (13), Satara (9), Solapur (3), Sangli (3), and Kolhapur (26) districts of Maharashtra were measured (Fig.1).

Results

In his study, the pure Bhimthadi horses were traced back to the Dhangar community (a Nomadic Tribe-C) in the state of Maharashtra. This tribe remains nomadic, and during their seasonal migrations with sheep and goat flocks, Bhimthadi horses are used for transporting household goods, poultry, and family members of livestock owners. During rainy season, these nomads they return to their native place, where the measurements were carried and other information collected. The population of horses in the tract was 8123 (Livestock Census, 2019). Considering the reduction rate in horse population as well as the proportion of pure Bhimthadi horses; the population of Bhimthadi breed has been estimated to be 5,134 with 575 stallions, 2300 gelds, 1540 mares and 719 foals. The average herd size was observed to be of five animals.

Fig. 2 Bhimthadi horses. A: Stallion, B: Mare, C: Mare and Foal, D: Foal.

(A) Bhimthadi Stallion

(B) Bhimthadi Mare

(C) Bhimthadi Mare and Foal

(D) Bhimthadi Foal

In terms of physical characteristics, the predominant coat colour of the Bhimthadi horse is chestnut, though other colours such as roan, bay, dark bay, grey, and skewbald are also observed. The forehead is generally flat, and the ears are relatively large. Unlike breeds such as the Marwari and Kathiawari, the ear tips of the Bhimthadi do not meet or overlap when rotated (Singh et al., 2002; Gupta et al., 2012 and 2014). The hooves are nearly round in shape with strong soles and walls, adapted for carrying loads on hilly terrain. These horses are typically not shod. The tail is well-set and adds to the overall appearance of the animal. The back is moderate and slightly arched (concave). The front and rear cannon bones are perpendicularly aligned between the knee/hock and fetlock joints, reflecting their adaptation for transporting people and goods across rugged terrain. These horses often travel long distances throughout the year due to the nature of the landscape. The average weight of males

at birth (0–1 month) was 43 kg and in adulthood (≥ 3 years) was 267 kg, while females weigh 40 kg at birth (0–1 month) and in adulthood 252 kg (≥ 3 years). The average height at withers, body length, heart girth and body weight was recorded as 130.3 ± 0.20 cm, 132.5 ± 0.25 cm, 142.0 ± 0.56 cm and 266.77 ± 2.22 kg for stallions and 129.7 ± 0.37 cm, 131.7 ± 0.42 cm, 139.7 ± 0.98 cm and 252.18 ± 3.76 kg for mares. The details regarding morphometric measurements of Bhimthadi horses has been presented in Table 1 and the photographs of Bhimthadi stallions, mare and foal have been presented in Fig.2.

Reproductively, Bhimthadi horses are quite active. Males attain puberty at around $2\frac{1}{2}$ years of age and are used for breeding from 3 years of age. Females exhibit their first oestrus at approximately $2\frac{1}{2}$ years and usually conceive for the first time at around 3 years. The oestrus cycle is of 21 days, with the oestrus (heat) period lasting for about 6 days. The gestation period is approximately 340 days, and the service period is about 60 days.

Table 1. Morphometric measurements of Bhimthadi stallions and mares.

Parameter	Stallion = 239		Mare = 134	
	Average	Range	Average	Range
Height at withers (cm)	130.3 ± 0.20	114-140	129.7 ± 0.37	114-140
Height at croup (cm)	$129.3 \pm 0.23^*$	113-138	$128.2 \pm 0.42^*$	110-135
Body length (cm)	132.5 ± 0.25	118-142	131.7 ± 0.42	107-142
Heart girth (cm)	$142.0 \pm 0.56^*$	126-160	$139.7 \pm 0.98^*$	118-159
Face length (cm)	$52.0 \pm 0.24^{**}$	42-58	$50.9 \pm 0.32^{**}$	42-57
Face width (cm)	19.0 ± 0.10	14-22	19.0 ± 0.14	14-22
Ear length (cm)	15.0 ± 0.13	10-18	14.9 ± 0.17	10-18
Ear width (cm)	10.0 ± 0.08	7-15	10.0 ± 0.11	7-15
Space between Eyes (cm)	17.0 ± 0.11	11-21	17.0 ± 0.14	11-21
Length of fore arm (cm)	$91.0 \pm 0.23^*$	79-98	$90.2 \pm 0.30^*$	79-97
Height at knee (cm)	$38.0 \pm 0.29^*$	30-48	$37.0 \pm 0.41^*$	29-48
Height at hock (cm)	$45.0 \pm 0.27^*$	35-55	$44.0 \pm 0.48^*$	33-55

Distance between fetlock to coronet (cm)	9.0±0.06**	7-11	8.5±0.10**	7-11
Chest width (cm)	27.0±0.08**	24-30	26.0±0.19**	22-30
Shank circumference (cm)	17.5±0.08**	13-19	16.9±0.11**	13-19
Throat latch (cm)	67.0±0.33**	44-72	63.3±0.45**	44-72
Poll to withers length (cm)	70.0±0.26	61-77	69.5±0.29	60-76
Distance between withers and croup (cm)	66.5±0.28	58-76	66.0±0.35	55-76
Distance between croup and head of tail (cm)	30.0±0.18**	25-35	28.4±0.24**	22-33
Tail Length (cm)	72.0±0.96	39-100	70.0±1.16	35-100
Body Weight (kg)	266.77±2.22**	175-333	252.18±3.76**	148-328

*Significant (P<0.05); **Significant (P<0.01)

It was also identified that they are not closely related with other breeds found in the breeding tract as well as the breeds found in the geographically nearby area i.e. Marwari and Kathiawari, which are quite distinct from it in terms of body size and other morphometric traits (Singh et al., 2002; Gupta et al., 2012 and 2014, Mehta et al., 2024). (Table 2).

Table 2. Phenotypic differences between Marwari, Kathiawari and Bhimthadi breeds of horse

S. No.	Qualities	Marwari	Kathiawari	Bhimthadi
1	Temperament	Alert	Alert	Active
2	Coat Colour	Brown, Black, Bay, Piebald and Skewbald are common	Chestnut, dun, bay sometimes gray but not black.	Predominant colour is Chestnut. However, Roan, Bay, Dark Bay, Grey, Skew Bald are also found but not black.
3	Head / Facial Markings	Star, Star and strip, Snip and Blaze are less commonly seen than Bhimthadi.	Star, Star and strip, Snip and Blaze are less commonly seen than Bhimthadi.	Most of the horses of Bhimthadi breed typically have either Star, Star and strip, Snip, Blaze and Strip & snip. Bald face is generally not seen.
4	Head	Long and convex profile	Small and Concave profile	Medium and flat profile
5	Fore Head	Not very broad	Broad	Not very broad

6	Nose (Frontal Bone)	Not chiseled	Chiseled	Not chiseled
7	Ears	Medium sized, the tip of ears touches when ears are rotated by 180°	Small sized, the tip of ears overlaps when ears are rotated by 180°	Large sized, the tip of ears remains far away when rotated.
8	Eyes	Normal	Large	Normal
9	Muzzle	Medium	Short	Medium
10	Nostrils Size & Shape	Medium and oval	Large and oval	Medium and oval
11	Neck Size & Shape	Long and thin	Stout and crested	Short and stout
12	Back	Long	Short (Saddle-Kathi shaped)	Short, slightly arched
13	Legs	Long and thin	Long and thin	Long and stout
14	Leg Markings	Sock, pastern and coronet are seen but less common than Bhimthadi	Sock, pastern and coronet are seen but less common than Bhimthadi	Stocking, sock, pastern and coronet, are very common
15	Hind Quarters	Broad, deep well muscular	Strong well developed, Broad	Strong well developed

Discussion

These attempts led to the recognition of the Bhimthadi as an independent breed, and on December 9, 2024, through a gazette notification, it was recognized as the eighth horse breed of India. This marks an important step toward conservation efforts for this historically significant yet endangered horse breed and opens the door to structured breeding programs, research initiatives, and promotional activities that could help reverse its decline. The breed exhibits a unique suite of characteristics that have allowed it to thrive in the hilly terrains of its native tract. Their small stature is perfectly suited for navigating the narrow paths and steep ridges. Furthermore, their deep chest signifies a superior breathing capacity, which is crucial for exertion at altitude. The hooves are remarkably well-adapted, being nearly round with strong soles and walls to handle load-bearing across difficult ground. The perpendicular alignment of the front and rear cannon bones reflects their innate suitability for transporting both people and goods over rugged terrain. Thus, these horses are exceptionally well-adapted to the specific landscapes and consistently migrate throughout the year. This unique

combination of morphometric traits reflects a sustained adaptation to the breeding tract, having been shaped by ancestors to meet the specific requirements of their owners. The Bhimthadi horse represents a living link to India's rich equestrian heritage and military history. Its unique combination of historical significance, physical capabilities, and cultural value makes its preservation not only desirable but essential for maintaining India's equine genetic diversity and cultural legacy.

Inspired by the rediscovery of Maharashtra's lost equine glory, the All India Bhimthadi Horse Association was formed and registered under the Companies Act, 2013 (18 of 2013), with Corporate Identity Number (CIN) U94990PN2023NPL223782, for the conservation, propagation, and improvement of Bhimthadi horses—particularly in view of the fact that only a few good stallions and mares remain, mainly in the hands of nomadic communities. The association has been wisely formed by inviting the descendants of the post bearers in the Maratha army during 17th-18th century. The successful organization of the Bhimthadi Horse Shows in 2024 and 2025 stands to the credit of this newly formed association. The society has initiated the registration process for the breeders and started micro-chipping of the animals for identification. A breeding plan has also been decided and development of these horses for the indigenous equestrian sports is underway. The Pony Club, UK has been contacted and it is the wish of the post bearers of the society that similar activities can be planned and executed for the propagation and development of Bhimthadi horse. The uniqueness of the breed has also been established through molecular studies. Thus, the glory of the breed began to shine once again, and its essence reached to one of the most prestigious animal conservation projects—Vantara—where a decision was taken to include Bhimthadi horses in its conservation and propagation program.

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